

ISic3502

I.Sicily inscription 3502

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.10.21

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 22653

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336196

1. [(?)χαίροις π]αροδείτα vac.
2. vacat
3. [ὁ δεῖνα κηρύξας] καὶ σαλπίσας ν
4. [— — — — — δ]ρόμοις κερκησίο [ις]
5. [ἐνθάδε κείται(?)].
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645370

PHI 336196

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1333

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 69 no.66 fig.148

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